

quite readily deep blue to blue green sparingly soluble dichloro mono (1-phenylamidino-*o*-alkylurea) copper(II) in almost quantitative yield. This latter reaction appears to be general and occurs with ease with unsubstituted dicyandiamide as well, which has escaped the attention of Dutta and Rây¹.

Reaction of copper(II) nitrate with phenyldicyandiamide in 1 : 1 ratio in *ethanol* gives a green powder which has been identified as di(nitrato) mono (1-phenylamidino-*o*-ethylurea) copper(II). Copper(II) sulphate (1 mol.) and phenyldicyandiamide (1 mol.) in *methanol* gives green coloured sulphato mono(1-phenylamidino-*o*-methylurea) copper(II). Phenyldicyandiamide has a strong sharp nitrile band at 2222 cm⁻¹ which is completely absent in the alcohol addition products. There is no C=O stretch at 1740 cm⁻¹ indicating that the products are not substituted guanylureas. Instead all the complexes have C-O-R stretch at ~ 1124 cm⁻¹ to support the 1-phenylamidino-*o*-alkylurea structure.

The infrared spectrum of the sulphato complex (1166, 1096, 1000, 958 cm⁻¹) shows evidence of bidentate sulphato group⁷. The bis(ligand) copper(II) nitrate and chloride salts are as expected biunivalent electrolytes in methanol while the dinitrato and the dichloromono (ligand) copper(II) complexes are substantially ionised in methanol, their conductivity increasing with dilution. This indicates that the coordinated nitrate and chloride are being solvolysed. The sulphato- and the nitrato mono(ligand) copper(II) complexes have no parallel yet in the metal biguanide chemistry⁸, and they also constitute the first examples reported in the family of 1-amidino-*o*-alkylurea metal complexes.

⁹ The electronic spectra of bis(1-phenylamidino-*o*-alkylurea) copper(II) salts conform to a square planar [CuN₄] chromophore (λ_{\max} 18 kK in acetonitrile). Compare square planar bis(biguanide) copper(II)⁹ (19.1 kK in water); bis(1-amidino-*o*-alkylurea) copper(II)² (18.5 kK in water), bis(ethylenediamine) copper(II)¹⁰ (18.2 kK in water), tetrakis(benzimidazole) copper(II) perchlorate¹¹ (19.0 kK, solid phase).

Compared to copper(II), nickel(II) is much less efficient in forcing addition of alcohol to phenyldicyandiamide. A reaction of 1 mol. of nickel chloride and two mols. of phenyldicyandiamide takes around 40 hrs to go to completion while that with copper(II) takes 6-8 hrs. (both on steam bath). The nickel(II) complexes are orange yellow, diamagnetic and hence conform to [NiN₄] square planar geometry.

o-Chloro- and *p*-chlorophenyldicyandiamide also give similar reactions.

It is interesting to note that phenyldicyandiamide¹² (m.p. 197°) can be recovered in ~ 95% yield after refluxing in methanol for 40 hr (Found, m.p. 196°; N, 35.3; Calc. N, 35.0 per cent). Phenyldicyandiamide also remains unchanged after 60 hr reflux in ethanol (recovery ~ 95%, m.p. 196°, N, 35.1 per cent).

Details of these studies will be reported in due course.

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Application of Thermographic Analysis in the Studies of Reclaimed Rubber Compounds

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THERMOGRAPHIC analysis has recently been an important analytical tool in the field of polymer chemistry and technology. Differential thermal analysis (DTA) is being used frequently in the investigations of the influence of various factors on the thermogram characteristics of different elastomer systems^{1,2}.

In order to have some definite ideas on the thermal characteristics of reclaimed rubber under different perspectives a modified form of the DTA section of the Derivatograph of Paulik and coworkers³ has been fabricated in our laboratory. The instrument has been calibrated by using pure compounds like benzoic acid and phthalimide by way of checking their T_m values (which are well separated from each other). For comparative studies on heat of reaction, the instrument has been standardised against the known heat of reaction for the dehydration of copper sulphate pentahydrate utilizing its last peak area.

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Fig. 1—Effect of substitution of natural rubber (smoked sheet) by reclaim (whole tyre) in high-sulphur compound.

Despite the different modes of studies made in reclaimed rubber⁴, thermal analysis has not been carried out as yet. Keeping this point in consideration the present investigation has been undertaken to study the effect of substitution of natural rubber by reclaimed rubber (otherwise called reclaim) in high sulphur compounds, where the limiting proportion of sulphur (50 parts)^{5,6} has been used. The recipe of such compounds is shown in Table 1, and their DTA thermograms in Figure 1. Curves I and IV represent compounds based solely on natural

TABLE 1—FORMULATION OF COMPOUNDS* (PARTS BY WEIGHT) ANALYSED BY DTA

	I	II	III	IV
Smoked sheet	100.0	75.0	50.0	—
Reclaim	—	50.0	100.0	200.0
Stearic acid	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Zinc oxide	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
BA**	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Sulphur	50.0	50.0	50.0	50.0

rubber and reclaim respectively, whereas curves II and III are for compounds based on their blends. In general, three different regions have been noted—the T_m of the curative (here sulphur), curing exothermic region and the degradation region. The characteristic features of each thermogram such as peak area, initiation and peak temperatures, etc. can be noted from the curing exotherms (starting above 160° and ending

** Butyraldehyde aniline.

*The reclaim contains about 50% of rubber hydrocarbon. Therefore, the proportion of reclaim used is twice that of smoked sheet to be substituted.

near 260°) of these curves. Heat evolution is found to diminish on gradual replacement of natural rubber by reclaim, the rate of decrease being slow at first, then becomes much faster and finally becomes slow again. Rate of reaction as observed from the slope of the peak with respect to the base line does not show much of difference in compounds based on natural rubber-reclaim blends, except in compounds based entirely on either of the two rubbers. Initiation temperature is however, practically the same in compounds based on natural rubber or its blend containing a major portion of the former. On the other hand, the temperature of initiation in compounds based on reclaim or its blend with natural rubber containing loss by weight of the latter are almost identical. On comparison between blends, changes in the ratio of natural rubber to reclaim show some change in initiation temperature. Regarding peak temperatures, little differences have been noted in all the above compounds. An exotherm around 350° has been observed in case of the natural rubber based compounds (curve I).

Detailed investigations on the effect of different ingredients in compounds based on reclaim as well as its blends with different polymers are also being carried out in this laboratory. Results will be published later on.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes. Part VIII: 1-Histidinate bis(Biguanide) cobalt(III) and (aminoacidato) bis (biguanide) cobalt (III) Salts.

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HISTIDINE(I) (histH) may bind to a metal ion as a tridentate NNO donor¹⁻⁴ or as bidentate NN donor^{4,5} or bidentate NO donor⁶. Since cobalt(III) is consistently six coordinate in its complexes